

VIRTIGATION – Emerging viral diseases in tomatoes and cucurbits: Implementation of mitigation strategies for durable disease management

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Report on performance of selected plant materials exhibiting resistances against whiteflies, begomovirus and/or tobamovirus in semi-commercial conditions

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviations used

DAI	Days after infestation
DPI	Days post inoculation
RT-qPCR	Real-time quantitative reverse transcription PCR

Virus acronyms

CABYV	Cucurbit aphid-borne yellows virus, polerovirus
CCYV	Cucurbit chlorotic yellows virus, crinivirus
CMV	Cucumber mosaic virus, cucumovirus
CYSDV	Cucurbit yellow stunting disease virus, crinivirus
MWMV	Moroccan watermelon mosaic virus, potyvirus
ToBRFV	Tomato brown rugose fruit virus, tobamovirus
ToLCNDV	Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus, begomovirus
WMV	Watermelon mosaic virus, potyvirus
ZYMV	Zucchini yellow mosaic virus, potyvirus

1 PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

The deployment of genetic resistance in plants against viruses and their vector organisms is among the most effective strategies for viral disease control in crops, particularly in horticulturally valuable plants such as tomato and cucurbits. The advantages of genetic strategies are well established: they are cost-effective, have little or no negative impact on the environment, are straightforward to implement once traits are well characterized through breeding programs, and allow for pyramiding of multiple traits, thereby reducing the risk of more aggressive strains overcoming resistance.

The results of the VIRTIGATION project reported here describe the performance of plant genotypes claimed to be resistant or tolerant under field conditions to the emergent begomovirus Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (ToLCNDV) and the tobamovirus Tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV). In particular, with respect to whiteflies vectors for the first virus, the report highlights the strong potential of cucumber cultivars with reduced susceptibility to *Bemisia tabaci* for being used in breeding programs, offering the added benefit of reducing reliance on chemical pesticides and supporting more sustainable integrated pest management strategies. Regarding virus resistance, although seed companies currently offer cultivars with good agronomic performance when challenged by ToLCNDV, data generated for both zucchini and melon species indicate the continued presence of the virus in fields, often in combination with other unrelated viral pathogens, indicating that these cultivars remain hosts for ToLCNDV and despite they can tolerate infection under moderate pressure, the tolerance may be overcome when overall virus pressure becomes too high.

In the case of ToBRFV, the strategy of using scions and rootstocks heterozygous for resistance or tolerance has been evaluated, finding that resistant rootstocks were able to protect susceptible scions, but failed to do so following foliar inoculations, which leads to the recommendation of using grafted plants with both resistant scions and rootstocks. In a field trial, virus accumulation in leaves and fruits and symptom severity were assessed, showing high virus levels in all genotypes, despite the fact that tolerant cultivars displayed reduced disease symptoms compared to susceptible ones, and the effect on total yield was similar across genotypes, with significant yield losses observed in all cases.

Overall, our findings emphasize the need to further develop genetic resistance-based strategies to address these two pathogens in the future, incorporating resistances to vector organisms when applicable, and also considering the important role of mixed infections in the epidemiology of vector-disseminated viruses.

The results provide a snapshot of the current in field situation and how the recent developments in genetic resistance can contribute to strengthen crop resilience against these major viral threats.

2 INTRODUCTION

The use of genetic resistance in plants against viruses and their vector organisms has long been, and continues to be, one of the most preferred strategies for controlling viral diseases in crops. Breeding efforts have identified sources of genetic resistance in most crop species, or in closely related species from which the genes responsible for desirable traits can be transferred into the genetic pool of the target crop and incorporated into elite cultivars that are widely used. These genetic strategies offer numerous advantages, particularly their minimal or negligible impact on the environment, their straightforward implementation once the traits are well characterized and molecular markers are available for tracking during breeding programs, and their suitability for additive combinations or pyramiding of resistance genes. Nevertheless, risks remain: the ongoing arms race between viral pathogens and their vectors can lead to the emergence of strains capable of overcoming resistance. This possibility requires careful management of selection pressure, for example by alternating the prevalence of different resistance genes to enhance the durability of the overall strategy. The seed industry, and especially seed companies, are well aware of the benefits derived from genetic resistance. Consequently, they dedicate substantial resources and foster productive collaborations with academia, which together enable relatively rapid stabilization once new crises arise.

In this context, the VIRTIGATION project brings together research experts in plant virology, entomology, and plant genetics to provide the fundamental knowledge needed to address emerging viral pathogens. Among these are the begomovirus Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (ToLCNDV), efficiently transmitted by whiteflies, and the tobamovirus Tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV), which spreads easily through mechanical means. The present report includes chapters dedicated to the results of assays conducted by different partners under field and semi-field conditions. These studies explore the performance of plant materials from various cucurbit species against ToLCNDV and its vector, for example: cucumber against whitefly transmission, and zucchini and melon against natural virus infection, as well as genetically based strategies in tomato to combat ToBRFV infections, with approaches including the use of interspecific rootstocks for grafting, and the evaluation of resistant tomato genotypes.

It is important to highlight the multiple advantages of addressing these complex trials within the framework of a large consortium. First, the diversity of countries and regions involved makes it possible to compare phytosanitary situations across different contexts and apply findings to a wide range of cropping systems. The collaboration between UNICT, WUR and NRI contributed to the chapter on resistance to the vector. Also the contribution of the Volcani Institute was particularly valuable, as it enabled the initiation and successful completion of work on ToBRFV before its presence in Europe prompted the recent change in quarantine classification. Additional benefits arise from the collaboration among partners APREL and INRAE providing analytical capacities, and the assistance of CSIC and HuertaValle Hibri2 to CRAG for performing the field trials. Furthermore, the availability of NGS protocols developed within the consortium, and especially web-based tools such as EmWeb's Genome Detective, greatly accelerated the complete identification of the viruses present.

3 CHAPTER 1: SEMI-FIELD SCREENING OF CUCUMBER VARIETIES FOR RESISTANCE TO WHITEFLIES

Whiteflies are significant pests worldwide due to their ability to feed on various host plants, ranging from cultivated crops to ornamental and wild plant species, to which they are responsible to transmit devastating viruses. Among whiteflies, the Sweet potato whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci*, attracted a lot of attention for causing considerable losses in numerous agricultural productions. This species is currently recognized as a complex of over 40 morphologically indistinguishable species, which differ in their host range, life cycle parameters, geographic distribution, fecundity, resistance to insecticides, and virus transmission efficiency. Particularly, *B. tabaci* is recognized for its ability to transmit persistent circulative begomoviruses and non-circulative viruses to plants, which severely impact crops like tomatoes and cucurbits. The primary method for controlling this pest relies on chemical insecticides, whose frequent use, however, leads to harmful effects on non-target organisms and the environment, and also promotes resistance development in *B. tabaci* populations. Given the need to find new eco-sustainable strategies, exploiting host plant resistance mechanisms, which involve morphological, chemical, and physical traits, provides an alternative solution, as these characteristics can influence the pest's colonization, feeding, and oviposition behavior.

Given the strong presence of vegetable crop cultivation in southern Italy and the need for integrated pest management strategies against *B. tabaci*, experimental trials were conducted in the framework of the present project activity, aimed at evaluating cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) accessions for resistance to *B. tabaci* MED through a semi-field approach. Since screening diverse plant genotypes can reveal novel sources of resistance, resistance traits of cucumber genotypes characterized at Wageningen University and Research Centre (The Netherland) and already assessed under controlled laboratory conditions at the University of Greenwich (United Kingdom) (both partners of the project), were evaluated in a semi-field experiment carried out at the University of Catania (Italy), to validate the plant performance in a real Mediterranean cultivation environment.

3.1 Materials and methods

3.1.1 Cucumber genotypes

Out of the 110 genotypes characterized at Wageningen University and Research Centre (The Netherland), after a general screening by the University of Greenwich (United Kingdom), a total of 21 most promising genotypes were provided, although only 17 genotypes emerged after sowing (Table 3.1). The 17 cucumber genotypes, defined as treatments, were transplanted and maintained in plastic pots (4 L) containing a substrate composed of soil and peat (1:1), fertilized regularly, and considered for experimental trials. For convenience, the genotypes were assigned serial numbers from 1 to 17 (Table 3.1).

Table 3.1. List of the 17 genotypes evaluated

Genotype		
Serial number	Accession number	Species (accession name)
1	CGN19733	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (Lange Gele Tros)
2	CGN20208	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (Westlandse Halfflange Witte; Delftse Halfflange Witte)
3	CGN21608	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (Improved Long Green)
4	CGN20203	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (Shantung Thorny)

5	CGN22276	<i>Cucumis sativus</i>
6	CGN20932	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (Aibai; P1227210)
7	CGN21615	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (Santo)
8	CGN22247	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (Soiul Cornichon; Cus145/71)
9	CGN23965	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (I.C.4079)
10	CGN22999	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (JL-10 Dhillon)
11	CGN23000	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (JL-11 Dhillon)
12	CGN22995	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (JL-6 Dhillon)
13	CGN22997	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (JL-8 Dhillon)
14	CGN22297	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (K-75)
15	CGN23004	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (K-90)
16	CGN23417	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (Kheera)
17	CGN19819	<i>Cucumis sativus</i> (Puneri Klura; VIR 2803)

3.1.2 *Bemisia tabaci* colony

The rearing population of *B. tabaci* was collected from a greenhouse-grown eggplant crop in southeastern Sicily (province of Ragusa, 36.97134 lat.; 14.424505 long.) and maintained on eggplant plants in the insectarium of the Department of Agriculture, Food and Environmental Science (University of Catania), in insect-proof BugDorm cages (MegaView Science, Taichung, Taiwan), under controlled environmental conditions ($T = 25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, $\text{RH} = 65 \pm 5\%$, and photoperiod of 14L:10D hours). Before running the experiment, the species identity of *B. tabaci* was genetically determined on about 30 adults, collected from the abovementioned rearing.

3.1.3 Semi-field assays

Semi-field trials were conducted in the greenhouse at the Azienda Agraria Sperimentale (37.407367 lat.; 15.060784 long.) of the University of Catania, from March to June 2024, including both choice and no-choice tests with all 17 genotypes mentioned above, once six fully expanded leaves were reached.

3.1.3.1 Choice test

Through the choice test, the preference of *B. tabaci* between different genotypes of cucumber plants was assessed. The experiment was conducted in a completely randomized block design with 17 cucumber genotypes irrigated daily and randomly arranged in metal tables covered with an anti-insect net, each representing an experimental unit.

Five hundred ten unsexed adults of *B. tabaci*, previously collected from the cages of the insectarium, were released per experimental unit and their preference was assessed at 24, 48 and 72 hours after release by counting the number of adults on the abaxial surface of three leaves/plant (apical, median and basal) from 6 to 8 am with the aid of a mirror. At 21 and 28 days after the infestation (DAI), the presence of the whitefly was assessed by recording the number of eggs, nymphs, and pupae of the whitefly, respectively on three leaves/plant, using a stereomicroscope (Olympus Optical Co., Ltd., Tokyo, JP, Japan, SZX-ILLK200). In total, six replicates per experimental unit were considered.

3.1.3.2 No-choice test

With the no-choice test, the availability of genotypes for oviposition and their ability to support the development of immature stages of *B. tabaci* were assessed.

The test was carried out in a completely randomized design with 17 cucumber genotypes irrigated daily and individually arranged in plastic cylinders covered with an anti-insect net, each representing one experimental unit.

Thirty *B. tabaci* adults, previously collected from the insectarium cages, were released into each cylinder and removed after 7 days of exposure. At 7, 21, and 28 DAI, the numbers of eggs, nymphs, and subpupae were counted on three leaves per plant and recorded. Each treatment included six replicates in total.

3.1.4 Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted for both semi-field trials using Statistica 7.0 software. A one-way ANOVA followed by Bonferroni post hoc test ($p < 0.01$) was applied. For the choice test, the number of *B. tabaci* adults per cm^2 was assessed separately at 24, 48, and 72 hours after infestation. Similarly, the numbers of eggs, nymphs, and subpupae per cm^2 were analyzed individually at 21 and 28 days after infestation (DAI). In the no-choice test, the same analytical approach was used, with the biological stages of *B. tabaci*—eggs, nymphs, and subpupae—counted per cm^2 at 7, 21, and 28 DAI separately.

3.2 Results

3.2.1 Molecular identification of *Bemisia tabaci*

Molecular identification confirmed that the individuals used in the experiment belonged to *B. tabaci* MED, showing more than 99% sequence identity with reference sequences in the NCBI database (mtCOI gene).

3.2.2 Choice and no-choice assays

3.2.2.1 Choice test

In the choice test, the number of whitefly adults per cm^2 varied significantly among the different genotypes, at 24 ($F = 12.29$, $p < 0.01$), 48 ($F = 9.40$, $p < 0.01$), and 72 ($F = 5.08$, $p < 0.01$) hours after infestation (Figure 3.1, Table 3.2). At 24 hours after infestation, pairwise comparisons with Bonferroni adjustment revealed that genotype 17 was the least preferred by the adults with a mean of 0.08 ± 0.01 whitefly adults/ cm^2 , performing significantly better than many other genotypes. In contrast, genotype 4 was the most attractive to adults, with a mean of 0.5 ± 0.03 whitefly adults/ cm^2 , while the remaining genotypes reflected considerable phenotypic variability in the response at this time. At 48 hours after infestation, statistical analysis revealed no significant differences among most genotypes, although genotypes 4 and 13 supported significantly higher adult densities compared to the others, with a mean of 0.7 ± 0.1 and 0.63 ± 0.1 whitefly adults/ cm^2 , respectively.

At 72 hours after infestation, pairwise comparisons with Bonferroni adjustment revealed greater phenotypic variability among genotypes. Genotypes 6, 8, 11, and 14 harbored the lowest adult densities, significantly lower than many other genotypes, with a mean of 0.14 ± 0.03 , 0.14 ± 0.02 , 0.12 ± 0.02 and 0.14 ± 0.04 whitefly adults/ cm^2 , respectively. In contrast, genotype 5 showed the highest density of adults with a mean of 0.4 ± 0.04 whitefly adults/ cm^2 , while the remaining genotypes did not differ significantly from one another.

Figure 3.1. Number of adults of *B. tabaci* per cm² at 1 (a), 2 (b), and 3 (c) days after infestation in choice test.

Table 3.2. Number of *B. tabaci* adults (mean ± SE) per cm² at 24, 48, and 72 hours after infestation in a choice test. Letters indicate significant differences between genotypes.

Genotype serial number	Number of adults at 24h	Number of adults at 48h	Number of adults at 72h
1	0,301 ± 0,04 abc	0,289 ± 0,03 b	0,177 ± 0,02 ab
2	0,330 ± 0,02 abc	0,212 ± 0,03 ab	0,212 ± 0,02 abc
3	0,200 ± 0,03 abc	0,206 ± 0,02 ab	0,295 ± 0,06 abc
4	0,525 ± 0,03 c	0,701 ± 0,13 c	0,253 ± 0,04 abc
5	0,312 ± 0,03 abc	0,194 ± 0,02 ab	0,401 ± 0,04 c
6	0,165 ± 0,02 ab	0,065 ± 0,01 a	0,141 ± 0,03 ab
7	0,342 ± 0,03 abc	0,283 ± 0,04 b	0,354 ± 0,04 abc
8	0,342 ± 0,04 abc	0,159 ± 0,04 ab	0,141 ± 0,02 ab
9	0,271 ± 0,01 abc	0,283 ± 0,04 b	0,224 ± 0,02 abc
10	0,377 ± 0,04 bc	0,289 ± 0,04 b	0,33 ± 0,03 abc
11	0,194 ± 0,02 abc	0,177 ± 0,03 ab	0,118 ± 0,02 a
12	0,147 ± 0,02 ab	0,177 ± 0,03 ab	0,165 ± 0,03 ab
13	0,277 ± 0,04 abc	0,631 ± 0,11 c	0,277 ± 0,04 abc
14	0,177 ± 0,03 ab	0,242 ± 0,02 ab	0,141 ± 0,04 ab
15	0,300 ± 0,04 abc	0,248 ± 0,04 ab	0,242 ± 0,05 abc
16	0,171 ± 0,03 ab	0,242 ± 0,03 ab	0,224 ± 0,04 abc
17	0,08 ± 0,01 a	0,306 ± 0,06 b	0,248 ± 0,04 abc

Regarding the population density of *B. tabaci* on the different cucumber genotypes, significant differences were observed at 21 days after infestation (Figure 3.2, Table 3.3). The lowest infestation levels were observed in genotype 6, which exhibited a very low egg density (0.005 ± 0.001 eggs/cm²) and the fewest nymphs (0.013 ± 0.002 nymphs/cm²). Similarly, genotype 11 showed no egg presence and a reduced nymph density (0.029 ± 0.007 nymphs/cm²). Genotype 9 had a slightly higher average

egg density (0.031 ± 0.010 eggs/cm²), but nymphal development remained limited (0.070 ± 0.019 nymphs/cm²).

In contrast, genotype 4 showed the highest infestation levels, with 0.158 ± 0.032 eggs/cm² and 0.372 ± 0.041 nymphs/cm², which were significantly higher than those of the least infested genotypes, 6 and 11 (eggs: $F = 16.88$, $p < 0.001$; nymphs: $F = 14.28$, $p < 0.001$). Genotype 5 also exhibited a similarly high egg density (0.158 ± 0.017 eggs/cm²) and a substantial nymph count (0.309 ± 0.027 nymphs/cm²). Other genotypes with elevated overall infestation levels included 13, 12, and 8, all of which had significantly higher egg and nymph densities compared to genotypes 6 and 11 ($F = 14.96$, $p < 0.001$). At 28 days after infestation, significant differences in the number of *B. tabaci* subpupae were again observed among the cucumber genotypes ($F = 4.98$, $p < 0.01$) (Table 3.3). Pupal counts varied across treatments, with a mean of 0.04 ± 0.01 pupae/cm² in genotypes 5 and 9, and ranged to 0.15 ± 0.02 and 0.17 ± 0.01 pupae/cm² in genotypes 10 and 4, respectively. The higher subpupal densities found in genotypes 4 and 10 indicate greater susceptibility to infestation or suggest that these genotypes may offer more favorable conditions for whitefly development.

Figure 3.2. Eggs (a) and nymphs (b) at 21 DAI and psubupae (c) at 28 DAI (mean \pm SE) of *B. tabaci* per cm² of leaf in the choice test.

Table 3.3. Eggs and nymphs at 21 DAI and subpupae at 28 DAI (mean \pm SE) of *B. tabaci* per cm² of leaf in the choice test. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different from each other according to Bonferroni's test ($p < 0.01$).

Genotype serial number	Number of eggs at 21 DAI	Number of nymphs at 21 DAI	Number of pupae at 28 DAI
1	0.017 \pm 0.012 abc	0.230 \pm 0.035 def	0.079 \pm 0.012 abc
2	0.056 \pm 0.007 abc	0.179 \pm 0.028 bcde	0.109 \pm 0.016 abc
3	0.070 \pm 0.012 abc	0.224 \pm 0.025 def	0.097 \pm 0.019 abc
4	0.158 \pm 0.032 de	0.372 \pm 0.041 f	0.170 \pm 0.014 c
5	0.158 \pm 0.017 d	0.309 \pm 0.027 ef	0.039 \pm 0.012 a
6	0.005 \pm 0.001 a	0.013 \pm 0.002 a	0.051 \pm 0.016 ab
7	0.003 \pm 0.001 a	0.171 \pm 0.031 bcde	0.112 \pm 0.018 abc
8	0.088 \pm 0.016 bcde	0.193 \pm 0.037 cde	0.088 \pm 0.017 abc
9	0.031 \pm 0.010 ab	0.070 \pm 0.019 abc	0.038 \pm 0.008 a
10	0.031 \pm 0.005 ab	0.070 \pm 0.010 abc	0.146 \pm 0.022 bc
11	0.000 \pm 0.000 a	0.029 \pm 0.007 ab	0.069 \pm 0.015 ab
12	0.121 \pm 0.011 cde	0.178 \pm 0.033 bcde	0.122 \pm 0.022 abc
13	0.083 \pm 0.015 bc	0.180 \pm 0.021 bcde	0.130 \pm 0.021 abc
14	0.007 \pm 0.002 a	0.108 \pm 0.021 abcd	0.095 \pm 0.010 abc
15	0.085 \pm 0.010 bcd	0.050 \pm 0.006 abc	0.052 \pm 0.019 ab
16	0.030 \pm 0.008 ab	0.107 \pm 0.030 abcd	0.110 \pm 0.023 abc
17	0.024 \pm 0.008 ab	0.094 \pm 0.027 abcd	0.056 \pm 0.018 ab

3.2.2.2 No-choice test

Under no-choice test conditions, the numbers of eggs, nymphs, and subpupae were assessed at 7, 21, and 28 DAI, respectively. At 7 DAI, a significant effect of genotype was detected ($F = 19.51$, $p < 0.001$). No eggs were recorded on genotype 6, whereas genotypes 10, 12, and 8 supported the highest oviposition levels, with genotype 10 exhibiting the greatest density (0.18 ± 0.02 eggs/cm²).

At 21 DAI, nymph densities differed significantly among genotypes ($F = 5.28$, $p < 0.001$). The highest infestations were observed on genotypes 10 and 1 (0.11 ± 0.02 and 0.11 ± 0.03 nymphs/cm²), whereas genotypes 2, 4, 16, 17, and 6 exhibited the lowest densities, with values significantly lower than those of genotypes 10 and 1 (Table 3.4).

At 28 DAI, significant differences were also detected in pupal density ($F = 5.42$, $p < 0.001$). Genotype 10 showed the highest level of infestation (0.06 pupae/cm²), followed by genotype 3 (0.05 ± 0.00 pupae/cm²). Both genotypes 10 and 3 differed significantly from genotype 6, which harbored no pupae, as well as from genotypes 16, 12, 7, 14, 13, and 8 (Table 3.4).

Figure 3.3. Eggs at 7 DAI (a), nymphs at 21 DAI (b), and subpupae at 28 DAI (c) (mean \pm SE) of *B. tabaci* per cm² of leaf in the no-choice test.

Table 3.4. Eggs at 7 DAI, nymphs at 21 DAI, and subpupae at 28 DAI (mean \pm SE) of *B. tabaci* per cm² of leaf in the no-choice test. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different from each other according to Bonferroni's test ($p < 0.01$).

Genotype serial number	Number of eggs at 7 DAI	Number of nymphs at 21 DAI	Number of pupae at 28 DAI
1	0,08 \pm 0,01 bcd	0,11 \pm 0,03 b	0,02 \pm 0,00 abc
2	0,02 \pm 0,00 abc	0,01 \pm 0,01 a	0,03 \pm 0,00 abc
3	0,07 \pm 0,01 abcd	0,06 \pm 0,01 ab	0,05 \pm 0,00 bc
4	0,07 \pm 0,01 bcd	0,01 \pm 0,00 a	0,01 \pm 0,00 a
5	0,09 \pm 0,01 bcd	0,07 \pm 0,02 ab	0,02 \pm 0,00 abc
6	0,00 \pm 0,00 a	0,01 \pm 0,01 a	0,00 \pm 0,00 a
7	0,10 \pm 0,01 d	0,08 \pm 0,02 ab	0,00 \pm 0,00 a

8	0,17 ± 0,02 e	0,06 ± 0,01 ab	0,01 ± 0,00 ab
9	0,09 ± 0,02 cd	0,04 ± 0,00 ab	0,02 ± 0,00 abc
10	0,18 ± 0,02 e	0,11 ± 0,02 b	0,06 ± 0,00 c
11	0,03 ± 0,01 abcd	0,03 ± 0,00 ab	0,02 ± 0,00 abc
12	0,17 ± 0,02 e	0,07 ± 0,03 ab	0,00 ± 0,00 a
13	0,05 ± 0,01 abcd	0,08 ± 0,01 ab	0,01 ± 0,00 ab
14	0,01 ± 0,01 ab	0,01 ± 0,00 a	0,01 ± 0,00 ab
15	0,09 ± 0,01 cd	0,02 ± 0,01 ab	0,03 ± 0,00 abc
16	0,06 ± 0,01 abcd	0,01 ± 0,01 a	0,00 ± 0,00 a
17	0,09 ± 0,01 cd	0,09 ± 0,03 ab	0,03 ± 0,00 abc

3.3 Discussion

In the choice test, assessments conducted at 1, 2, and 3 days after *B. tabaci* infestation revealed a clear adult preference for genotype 4. By 3 DAI, genotype 12 also showed a notable increase in attractiveness. In contrast, genotypes 7 and 13 consistently ranked among the least preferred by the adults. This pattern was reflected in the later developmental stages of the whitefly. At 21 days after infestation, genotype 4 recorded the highest number of eggs and nymphs, while genotypes 7 and 13 consistently had the lowest counts. By 28 days, genotype 4 remained the most heavily infested, in terms of subpupae, with genotype 12 also showing a significant presence of subpupae. Genotype 7, however, continued to exhibit the lowest density of subpupae.

Under no-choice test conditions, the same trend was evident. At 7 days after infestation, genotypes 7 and 13 once again recorded the lowest egg counts, while genotype 12 was among the most heavily infested. This pattern persisted at 21 days, with genotype 7 showing the fewest nymphs and genotype 12 ranking among the most affected. By 28 days, the trend remained consistent: genotype 12 exhibited the highest density of subpupae, whereas genotype 7 continued to show minimal infestation.

The choice and no-choice tests highlighted clear variability among the 17 cucumber genotypes in terms of attractiveness and ability to support the development of *B. tabaci* MED. Some genotypes, namely 7 and 13, showed very low infestation levels and limited pest development, suggesting a high resistance potential.

In contrast, genotypes 4 and 12 exhibited high infestation rates and increased development of subpupae, indicating high susceptibility to *B. tabaci* MED.

The genotypic responses were generally consistent across both choice and no-choice tests, supporting the reliability of the findings and indicating that the observed differences are likely due to intrinsic genetic traits rather than random variation or environmental influences.

3.4 Conclusions

The resistant genotypes identified in this study showed strong potential for use in breeding programs aimed at developing cucumber cultivars with reduced susceptibility to *B. tabaci*. Such cultivars could help lower reliance on chemical pesticides and support more sustainable integrated pest management strategies.

Future research should focus on uncovering the specific resistance mechanisms involved, morphological and/or chemical, and on validating the performance of resistant genotypes by analyzing changes in *B. tabaci* probing and feeding behavior. Additionally, transmission experiments should be conducted to assess the whitefly's ability to spread viruses, particularly Tomato Leaf Curl New Delhi Virus (ToLCNDV), on these genotypes.

4 CHAPTER 2: AGRONOMIC PERFORMANCE OF NEW CUCURBIT CULTIVARS

The results described in this chapter served as a background or starting point to know the importance of mixed infections in a total of 11 zucchini cultivars selected by our partner APREL. They performed two rounds of experimentation in two seasons, 2024 and 2025, to evaluate their agronomic performance. The selected cultivars were chosen as representative of the new cultivars expected to be either resistant to ToLCNDV, or at least exhibit tolerance to this pathogen, allowing a commercially profitable cultivation by producers. Virus analysis were performed by INRAE partners.

4.1 Results from 2024

Six new zucchini cultivars were tested in 2024: J, E, F, B, C, L and five in 2025: A, D, G, H,I and B, C, E,F (already tested in 2024). All cultivars have an intermediate resistance to WMV, ZYMV and ToLCNDV, except the cultivar J which only has a theoretically expected good behaviour to ToLCNDV. Cultivars E and F had a significantly higher yield than the control, while the others had lower yields. The viral analysis (performed in the laboratory by partner INRAE) showed that WMV and CABYV were the most prevalent viruses being detected (in more than 60% of plants). ToLCNDV was detected in susceptible control in 50% of plants with 32% of symptomatic plants, indicating a situation of low to medium viral pressure characterized by presence of detectable virus in some plants that did not exhibited symptoms. Resistant cultivars presented only minor symptoms on 10 to 40% of plants, and the virus presence did not impact the growth of the plant or the production of fruits significantly. ToLCNDV was not detected in plants for 3 resistant cultivars (E,B,C) and in a few number of plants for resistant cultivars F and L. This results show a good opportunity for famers to dispose of resistant material.

4.2 Results from 2025

The second trial in 2025 gave different results. Indeed, the viral pressure was extremely high and none cultivars showed a good agronomic performance. The viral analysis showed a high proportion of plants infected by the ToLCNDV for all cultivars, even the ones considered to be resistant or tolerant (50 to 90% of plants). Severe symptoms appeared very early on leaves and on fruits. The susceptible control cultivar stopped growing at the first week of harvest and the resistant cultivar at the second week of harvest. Like in 2024, a co-infection with different virus was observed, including both CABYV and WMV, both being aphid transmitted viruses, which clearly indicated that both kind of vectors (whiteflies and aphids) were involved in the dispersal of viral pathogens and confirmed their presence in mixed infections.

Figure 4.1. Results of field trials conducted in 2024 (left) and 2025 (right). The upper graphs present the yields of the different materials, while the lower graphs show the percentages of plants infected by the indicated viruses.

In conclusion, although seed companies currently offer some cultivars with a good agronomic performance that claim to be resistant to ToLCNDV, our data indicate that the presence of the virus (often in combination with other unrelated viral pathogens) does indeed reduce symptoms on plants and fruits, but does not prevent the virus from being present in the analyzed plants. Consequently, these cultivars remain hosts for ToLCNDV, and while they can tolerate the attack of viruses under moderate pressure, this tolerance is overcome when the overall virus pressure becomes too high.

5 CHAPTER 3: FIELD TRIALS OF SELECTED MELON MATERIALS

This chapter reports the experiments performed by CRAG, with the leading role of postdoc Mireia Uranga Ruiz de Eguino, and PhD candidate Clara Ontañón, and in two settings within an area with expected high incidence of ToLCNDV through natural vector-mediated dissemination, and where other common viruses of cucurbits could be found in mixed infections. Essential assistance and support for the sampling procedures were provided by local collaborators, in particular Francisco Villanueva from Huerta Valle Hibri2, Juan Antonio Diaz Pendón from CSIC, and Juan Antonio Fernández from Agrotropiche S.L., a local company dedicated to provide agricultural services and with the status of project stakeholder.

The materials tested included susceptible cultivars such as Védraçais melon, kindly provided by partner Cecile Desbiez from INRAE, and used in tests in growth chambers during a brief stay of student Atiwich Patthamapornosirikul at CRAG, as reported separately (Deliverable 4.5). Other melon accessions and materials were selected for further testing with assistance of our collaborator Carmelo López del Rincón (COMAV, UPV, Valencia, Spain). Materials were propagated by partner HuertaValle Hibri2, and the seeds provided in due time to the collaborators for their germination following the usual procedures in the region of testing.

The melon materials to be compared were:

- PS-C61
- PS-Co
- P31
- P201
- PI 313970
- PI 414723

The two last accessions were selected by the presence of multiple resistances to viruses, in particular to ToLCNDV in the case of PI 414723, while the two first entries corresponded respectively to the susceptible "Piel de sapo", and a commercial cultivar with a good behavior in terms of productivity when ToLCNDV is present.

Regarding methodologies, collected field samples were preserved in RNA-later solution, and they were processed for RNA extraction along with selected laboratory-infected controls using the Maxwell® RSC Plant RNA Kit for automated isolation of total RNA from tissue samples using the Maxwell® RSC Instrument. The libraries were also prepared at CRAG by using the TrueSeq Stranded Total RNA Library Prep with Ribo-Zero Plant. This strategy includes steps for depletion of ribosomal RNAs, and successfully served to identify viruses with either RNA or DNA genomes, in the later case through analysis of virus-derived transcripts. Samples were sequenced (150 pair-ends) by Novogene as external provider. The analysis of data was done using the Genome Detective tool developed by VIRTIGATION partner EmWeb.

5.1 Field testing: locations

The locations selected for the trials are indicated in figure 5.1, and corresponded to one greenhouse and one open field. The greenhouse was chosen because it had a historical record of previous virus-related issues when growing cucurbits, and in this particular season was dedicated to zucchini,

considered a good reservoir for many viruses that could later move to other susceptible crops, including melon. The open field is situated in the upper part of a hilly area in the Axarquía region, with neighboring fields being cultivated often with tomato, cucurbits and other crops. In this case, the unique topography favors the “Levante” wind, which blows from the seaside toward the hilltops, and this wind might likely contribute to bring in different insects acting as vectors of viral pathogens circulating in the area, reaching the field where the melon varieties of interest were grown. Although at the time of sampling no large colonies of insects were observed upon visual inspection, the results of the molecular analysis (see below) confirmed that vectors of different taxa, aphids and whiteflies at least, had visited the location and inoculated indeed different viruses.

Figure 5.1. Location of greenhouse and field. The map shows the chosen location with zoomed views, and their coordinates are indicated below the aerial images. The right panel displays schematically the arrangement of the randomly distributed six tested melon materials in two rows at each location.

5.2 Field testing: cultivation conditions and sampling

The seeds of the materials were germinated and later transplanted in the chosen fields under the supervision of the collaborators, who also performed periodic visits to the fields, and provided images at different time points.

The expedition for the sampling was performed at the end of the growing season, with participation of CRAG personnel. Samples from symptomatic plants were taken, along with control samples, and the appearance of fruits fully developed by the time of sampling were also documented photographically.

Figures 5.2, 5.3 and 5.4 show respectively details of the greenhouse, open field and selected melon fruits.

Figure 5.2. Details of the greenhouse experiment. Views of the commercial greenhouse where the plants were located and at different dates, including the sampling period (photographs 1 to 4, from left to right). No clear viral symptoms were observed, except for yellowing of older leaves in some plants (shown in the upper right photograph). Below, selected fruits are shown at time of recollection.

Figure 5.3. Details of the open field experiment. Pictures in the upper part correspond to the location, with views of the surroundings (left), and a detail of highly severe virus symptoms in leaves (right), with mosaic, yellowing and distortion. Below, images of selected fruits are shown at time of recollection, with details of leaves with symptoms in some of the plants being sampled.

Figure 5.4. Phenotypes of the fruits of the selected melon materials collected at the sampling date (July 2025). On the left photograph, representative fruits were compared in size, while the detail photographs on the panels at the right side show longitudinally sectioned fruits to reveal internal traits like flesh colors and seeds.

5.3 Results: detection of viruses in field samples

The raw data submitted to the Genome Detective tool revealed the presence of several viruses in eight analyzed samples from seven individual plants. As an internal control, two samples from the same symptomatic plant (PS-Co genotype) were collected from leaf and fruit, respectively, and the results confirmed the presence of the same viral species in the two independently analyzed samples (not shown). Complete genome sequences of the following viruses were recovered from the entire collection of plant samples:

- 5 samples with the polerovirus **CABYV**
- 4 samples with the begomovirus **ToLCNDV**
- 3 samples with the potyvirus **MWMV**
- 2 samples with the crinivirus **CCYV**
- 1 sample with the cucumovirus **CMV**

Only one plant of the accession PI 313970 was considered free of viruses, since the reads assigned to viruses by the Genome Detective tool were fewer than one hundred and corresponded only to fragments with minimal genome coverages, thus falling below the threshold for contamination.

The tables below show the relevant information for each plant samples where a sufficient number of reads corresponding to viral sequences confirmed the infections. The numbers in the last column indicate the total number of different viruses (mixed infections) present in the same plant.

Table 5.1 includes the samples where ToLCNDV was detected, sorted according to the number of different viruses being detected. Table 5.2 shows samples free from the begomovirus, but with presence of other viruses.

Table 5.1. Viruses present in field samples with ToLCNDV

Sample	Genotype	Virus Name	Nb Reads	Genome Coverage	Depth Of Coverage	Virus	Num. viruses
1	PI 414723	Moroccan watermelon mosaic virus	2593290	99,97	32663,1	MWMV	1
		Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (DNA-A)	163456	100,00	7209,5	ToLCNDV	2
		Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (DNA-B)	15259	100,00	688,7		
		Polerovirus	3271	80,93	86,7	CABYV	3
		Cucurbit chlorotic yellows virus (RNA 2)	2665	99,52	40,5	CCYV	4
		Cucurbit chlorotic yellows virus (RNA 1)	796	98,51	11,3		
2	PS-Co	Moroccan watermelon mosaic virus	1948782	99,85	24214,3	MWMV	1
		Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (DNA-A)	121544	100,00	5266,4	ToLCNDV	2
		Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (DNA-B)	12057	100,00	536,2		
		Polerovirus	3392	99,38	71,2	CABYV	3
		Cucurbit chlorotic yellows virus (RNA 2)	1917	99,61	28,7	CCYV	4
		Cucurbit chlorotic yellows virus (RNA 1)	645	98,13	9,2		
3	PS-C61	Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (DNA-A)	32597	100,00	1433,8	ToLCNDV	1
		Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (DNA-B)	7684	100,00	351,9		
		Polerovirus	17378	86,81	424,2	CABYV	2
4	P201	Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (DNA-A)	11688	100,00	515,3	ToLCNV	1
		Tomato leaf curl New Delhi virus (DNA-B)	3544	100,00	160,7		

Table 5.2. Viruses present in field samples without begomovirus

Sample	Genotype	Virus Name	Nb Reads	Genome Coverage	Depth Of Coverage	Virus	Num. viruses
1	PS-Co	Moroccan watermelon mosaic virus	2389576	99,8972	30190,8	MWMV	1
		Potterovirus	36861	99,5414	792,6	CABYV	2
2	P201	Cucumber mosaic virus (RNA 3)	864567	100	47723,7		
		Cucumber mosaic virus (RNA 1)	977857	99,9404	35690,0	CMV	1
		Cucumber mosaic virus (RNA 2)	640801	99,9016	25805,5		
		Potterovirus	11037	99,4002	239,1	CABYV	2

It is relevant to indicate that CABYV, MWMV and CMV are transmitted by aphids, while the two others viruses ToLCNDV and CCYV found in the same location are transmitted by whiteflies, providing evidence of vector activity for both major insect groups.

Sequence analysis also allowed us to recover complete viral genome information, enabling comparisons with data available in the scientific literature. Knowing the sequences of circulating viruses will facilitate the design of primers to confirm the results by RT-PCR.

6 CHAPTER 4: INTERSPECIFIC ROOTSTOCKS SERVING AS BLOCKERS OF SOIL-MEDIATED TOBRFV INFECTION OF TOMATO PLANTS

A total of 52 wild tomato (*Solanum* spp.) accessions were screened for resistance to Tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV) through controlled inoculation assays. Resistance evaluation was based on both leaf Disease Severity Index (DSI), scored according to standardized symptom scales, and virus accumulation as determined by ELISA titers. Among the wild accessions tested, three were consistently ELISA-negative: *S. pennellii* 'LA0716', *S. pennellii* 'LA5240', and *S. chilense* 'LA1938', suggesting the absence of detectable viral replication in these genotypes.

In parallel, 45 cultivated tomato lines were subjected to the same inoculation protocol, with assessments including DSI in both leaves and fruits, as well as ELISA titers. Nine cultivated lines remained asymptomatic throughout the evaluation period, indicating potential tolerance or resistance to ToBRFV infection.

Inoculations were performed under controlled conditions to ensure reproducibility, and symptom scoring was complemented by serological assays to provide quantitative confirmation of viral presence or absence. The combination of phenotypic and molecular data allowed for a robust classification of resistance responses across the tested germplasm.

Further details of this work, including methodological descriptions and complete datasets, have already been reported in Deliverable D3.1, *Defined ToBRFV-resistant tomato varieties*.

Scions and rootstocks heterozygous for resistance to Tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV) were generated using selected ELISA-negative cultivated lines and the wild species *Solanum pennellii* 'LA5240' as resistance donors, respectively. Inoculation assays demonstrated that ToBRFV root inoculations of susceptible rootstocks were able to overcome scion resistance. Root inoculations were performed under stringent conditions, with truncated roots immersed in virus sap to ensure effective exposure.

When grafted tomato plants were subjected to ToBRFV root inoculation, resistant rootstocks were capable of protecting susceptible scions (Figure 6.1). However, resistant rootstocks failed to confer protection when susceptible scions were challenged through foliar inoculation. These findings indicate that the most effective strategy is the use of grafted plants combining resistant scions with resistant rootstocks.

In the field trial, evaluation of ToBRFV-induced fruit symptoms revealed that severity in the first three clusters was reduced when susceptible scions were grafted onto resistant rootstocks. In contrast, leaf symptom severity was not reduced under the same conditions. These results highlight the importance of combining resistance in both scions and rootstocks to achieve durable protection against ToBRFV

Figure 6.1. Challenging grafted tomato plants with ToBRFV infection via root- or foliar-inoculations

7 CHAPTER 5: TESTING TOBRFV-RESISTANT TOMATO GENOTYPES UNDER SEMI-COMMERCIAL CONDITIONS

Experimental Design

To evaluate resistance to Tomato brown rugose fruit virus (ToBRFV), a controlled experiment was conducted using four tomato genotypes: two previously characterized as resistant and two susceptible (Table 7.1).

Treatments Two treatments were applied: inoculated versus non-inoculated controls.

Plant Material and Replication For each genotype, three experimental blocks were established, each consisting of four plants, resulting in 12 plants per genotype. This design yielded 48 plants per treatment, and with two treatments applied, a total of 96 plants were included in the study.

Assays Plants were assessed for:

- **Disease Severity Index (DSI)**, based on visual symptom scoring.
- **Virus accumulation**, quantified by ELISA.
- **Yield performance**, measured across multiple harvests.

Experimental Timeline

- Sowing: 13 May 2024
- Transplanting: 16 June 2024
- Inoculation: 30 June 2024
- Symptom screening and virus quantification: 30 July 2024
- Harvests: 29 August, 15 September, 22 September, and 1 October 2024

Disease Severity Index (DSI) Scale

- 0 – No symptoms
- 1 – Mild mosaic in plant apex
- 2 – Severe mosaic in plant apex
- 3 – Leaf elongation and thread-like leaf morphology

This experimental design ensured robust replication and allowed for the systematic evaluation of symptom severity, viral load, and agronomic performance under controlled inoculation conditions.

Table 7.1. Tomato genotypes used in the experiment

Genotype	Acronim	ToBRFV	Segment
Eyfele	EYF	Susceptible	Mini-cluster oval; Indeterminate

Emyelle	EMY	Intermediate resistance	Mini-cluster oval; Indeterminate
Tylcram	TYL	Susceptible	Cluster; Indeterminate
TIPC	TIP	Intermediate resistance	Cluster; Indeterminate

Results:

Symptom severity (using the DSI scale of 0-to-3) and virus accumulation level (using ELISA) were determined 30 days after inoculation (Figure 7.1). All four genotypes contained high virus accumulation levels, resistant and susceptible alike. However, the two resistant genotypes showed low ToBRFV-induced disease symptoms compared to the two susceptible genotypes (Figure 7.1).

Looking at ToBRFV effect on total yield (Figure 7.2), it seems that the different genotypes reacted in the same manner regardless of whether the genotype was resistant or susceptible to the virus. Both mini-cluster genotypes showed a significant yield loss due to inoculation with ToBRFV – the resistant genotype EMY lost 18% of its yield while the susceptible genotype EYF lost 29% of its yield. Both the cluster genotypes TYL (susceptible) and TIP (resistant) showed no-yield reduction following inoculation with ToBRFV. However, it should be noted that the total yield of all four genotypes was low (Figure 7.2)

Figure 7.1. Disease index severity and virus level 30 days after inoculation

Figure 7.2. Effect of ToBRFV on total yield per plant.